

The Reduction of *o*-Nitrotoluene.

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The reduction of *o*-nitrotoluene does not seem to have been so systematically studied as the reduction of other nitro-hydrocarbons of the aromatic series. Petrieff (*Ber.*, 1873, 6, 557) and Goldschmidt (*Ber.*, 1878, 11, 1624) seem to be the earliest workers who appear to have obtained a tolidine from *o*-nitrotoluene through hydrazotoluene. Klinger (*Ber.*, 1882, 15, 865) obtained by the action of sodium methylate on *o*-nitrotoluene red amorphous bodies, none of which he could purify and identify. Haussermann (*Chem. Zeit.*, 1893, 17, 129, 209) carried on the electrolytic reduction of *o*-nitrotoluene in alcoholic solution (6-8 amperes, 6 volts) and obtained hydrazotoluene first and tolidine later on at the cathode. Evans and Fry (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 26, 1161) reduced *o*-nitrotoluene by means of magnesium amalgam and obtained a 50 per cent. yield of *o*-azoxytoluene in the presence of ethyl alcohol and a 66.5 per cent. yield of *o*-azotoluene in the presence of methyl alcohol. van Loon (*Chem. Weekblad*, 1908, 5, 689) mentions to have obtained a good yield of tolidine from hydrazotoluene. While studying the action of the Grignard's reagent on aromatic nitro-compounds, Hepworth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1004), obtained ethyl- (or methyl)-*o*-toluidine and 2:2-azotoluene by means of magnesium powder and ethyl (or methyl) bromide. Zechmeister and Rom (*Ber.*, 1926, 59, 867) obtained the azoxy-derivative by reducing *o*-nitrotoluene by means of magnesium turnings in presence of a large quantity of methyl alcohol and a saturated aqueous solution of ammonium chloride.

It will thus be seen that no systematic work has been carried out on the reduction of *o*-nitrotoluene. It was therefore thought desirable to investigate the subject thoroughly and find out the exact

conditions under which different reduction products could be obtained by using different reducing agents.

The present paper includes the results obtained by using various reducing agents such as sodium methylate, sodium ethylate, alcoholic potash, magnesium powder, aluminium dust, zinc dust, hydrogen sulphide in alcoholic ammoniacal solution, sodium arsenite, zinc and ammonium chloride solution in presence of alcohol, sulphides of heavy metals in alkaline solutions, iron in presence of sodium chloride solution, sodium disulphide, stannous chloride in an alkaline or in an acid solution and tin and hydrochloric acid. By using these reducing agents under different conditions *o*-azoxytoluene, *o*-azotoluene, *o*-hydrazotoluene and *o*-toluidine have been obtained.

o-Azoxytoluene has been obtained in more or less yield by means of magnesium powder in presence of methyl or ethyl alcohol and ammonium chloride solution, zinc dust or aluminium dust or stannous chloride in alkaline solutions and hydrogen sulphide in alcoholic ammoniacal solutions. A better yield is, however, obtained by means of zinc dust in presence of ammonium chloride solution at 100°.

o-Azotoluene is the main product when *o*-nitrotoluene is reduced by means of sodium methoxide or ethoxide at 100° or by means of aluminium wire (or dust) or zinc dust and caustic soda solution at 100°. By reduction with stannous chloride in an alkaline solution some azo-compound along with azoxy-compound is obtained. By reducing azoxytoluene by means of zinc dust or phosphorus pentachloride, azotoluene is also obtained.

o-Hydrazotoluene is obtained along with *o*-azotoluene when aluminium or zinc dust in an alkaline solution is used. This compound is also obtained when *o*-azotoluene is reduced by means of alcoholic ammonium sulphide.

Small quantities of *o*-toluidine are found in the end products when reduction is carried on by sodium methoxide, sodium ethoxide or aluminium dust in caustic soda solution. A fairly good yield of *o*-toluidine is obtained by reduction with sodium disulphide, or by stannous chloride in an acid solution, or by tin and hydrochloric acid.

No reduction product has been obtained by sodium arsenite, or by the sulphides of heavy metals in an alkaline solution or by iron and sodium chloride solution or by means of benzoin.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Reduction of o-Nitrotoluene to o-Azoxytoluene.

1. *By means of magnesium powder.* The reducing action of magnesium powder on *o*-nitrotoluene in presence of methyl or ethyl alcohol and a saturated aqueous solution of ammonium chloride has been studied in a series of experiments (see Table I) to find out the exact conditions under which the maximum yield of the reduction product may be obtained. The experiment has usually been carried out by taking *o*-nitrotoluene (12 g.), adding to it methyl or ethyl alcohol (150 c.c.) and a saturated solution of ammonium chloride or other salts (150 c.c.) and then a certain quantity of magnesium powder and heating the mixture on a water-bath in a flask provided with an upright condenser for 6 to 7 hours. At the end of the reaction, the product is filtered while still hot, the alcohol distilled off and the residue treated with excess of water. It is again filtered and the residue is extracted with alcohol and crystallised. The product in most cases has been found to melt sharply at 58.5° and identified to be *o*-azoxytoluene.

The experiment of Zechmeister and Rom (*loc. cit.*) has been repeated but we could not obtain the same yield as claimed by the authors. It has been possible, however, to get a much larger yield by changing the proportions of the reagents used. Methyl and ethyl alcohols have been tried and a proportionately larger yield of the *o*-azoxy-compound has been obtained in the case of ethyl alcohol. In place of ammonium chloride, other compounds such as sodium chloride, aluminium chloride and ammonium sulphate have also been used. Sodium and aluminium chlorides are quite ineffective whilst ammonium sulphate has been found to yield a certain quantity of the azoxy-compound. From this it seems that the ammonium radicle is responsible for the catalytic action and not the chloride ion.

2. *By means of zinc dust in a neutral medium.* Experiments similar to the above have been carried on with the only difference that zinc dust has been used in place of magnesium powder. *o*-Azoxytoluene has been obtained in this case also but the yield is very small. Zinc dust is therefore found to be not so effective a reducing agent as magnesium powder under similar conditions.

3. *By means of zinc dust in an alkaline medium.* *o*-Nitrotoluene (12 g.) and ethyl alcohol (150 c.c.) are put in a flask provided with an upright condenser. Zinc dust (25 g.) is added to it and then a 30 per cent. sodium hydroxide solution (200 c.c.). The reaction is allowed to proceed at the room temperature for one hour. It is then gently warmed for a short time in a water-bath and filtered while still hot. The alcohol in the filtrate is distilled off and the residue filtered off and washed with water. It is dried and extracted with alcohol and crystallised. Thus pure *o*-azoxytoluene (3.6 gm.) is obtained.

4. *By means of aluminium wire in an alkaline medium.* Experiment similar to (3) is carried on with aluminium wire in place of zinc dust. The yield of the azoxy-derivative is still poor, being about 20 per cent.

5. *By means of stannous chloride in an alkaline medium.* *o*-Nitrotoluene (12 g.) is taken in a flask provided with an upright condenser and a 60 per cent. sodium hydroxide solution (50 c.c.) is added. Alcohol (150 c.c.) together with stannous chloride (15 g.) are also added and the mixture is heated on a water-bath for about 4 hours. The alcohol is then distilled off, the residual product treated with dilute hydrochloric acid to remove the alkali, and filtered. The residue on the filter-paper is dried, extracted with hot absolute alcohol and crystallised. *o*-Azoxytoluene (about 4.5 g.) is obtained. The experiment has been repeated with 20, 25 and 30 g. respectively of stannous chloride but no change is observed either in the quantity or the nature of the product obtained. It has been found, however, that if the duration of reaction is increased to eight hours when 15 gm. of stannous chloride are taken, 4 gm. of *o*-azoxytoluene and 2.5 gm. of *o*-azotoluene are obtained. The reduction of *o*-nitrotoluene by means of stannous chloride in alkaline medium to the amino-compound is not effected as in the case of nitrobenzene.

6. *By means of hydrogen sulphide in an ammoniacal medium.* Attempts have been made to reduce *o*-nitrotoluene by means of hydrogen sulphide at the ordinary temperature in presence of ammonia and alcohol. With 12 gm. of *o*-nitrotoluene, only 0.8 gm. of *o*-azoxytoluene is obtained after two hours and the reduction does not proceed further to any appreciable extent. No improvement in the yield was observed on conducting the experiment at 60°.

TABLE I.

o-Nitrotoluene taken = 12 gm.

Expt.	Reducing agent (gm.).	Methyl or ethyl alcohol (c.c.).	Medium : a saturated so- lution (c.c.).	Percentage yield of <i>o</i> -azoxytoluene.
	<i>Magnesium</i>	<i>Methyl alcohol</i>	<i>Ammonium chloride</i>	
1	6	150	150	85.4
2	10	"	"	62.7
3	12	"	"	66.6
4	15	"	"	88.7
		<i>Ethyl alcohol</i>		
5	6	150	"	42.4
6	8	"	"	65.7
7	12	"	"	72.7
			<i>Sodium chloride</i>	
8	"	"	150	Very little.
			<i>Aluminium chloride</i>	
9	"	"	150	Nil.
			<i>Ammonium sulphate</i>	
10	"	"	150	48.5
	<i>Zinc</i>		<i>Ammonium chloride</i>	
11	12	"	150	12.3
12	16	"	"	13.4
			<i>Sodium hydroxide</i>	
13	25	"	200 (30%)	36.1
	<i>Aluminium</i>			
14	5	5	"	20.2
	<i>Stannous chloride</i>			
15	15	"	100	45.5
16	20	"	"	55.6
17	<i>Hydrogen sulphide</i>	"	<i>Ammoniacal</i>	8.1

Remarks.—In expts. 1-14 heating on a water-bath was continued for 6-7 hours. In expts. 15 and 16, the duration of heating was 4 hours. Expt. 17 was conducted at room temp. for one hour.

Reduction of o-Nitrotoluene to o-Azotoluene.

7. *Reduction by means of sodium methoxide.* Sodium is dissolved in an excess of methyl alcohol and the solution is added to *o*-nitrotoluene in a flask provided with an upright condenser and heated on a water-bath for 8 hours. The excess of methyl alcohol is then distilled off. The product is then shaken with a large excess of water to dissolve out the sodium formate formed in the reaction and filtered. The residue is purified by repeated crystallisation from ether. The product so obtained forms red monoclinic crystals and is identified to be *o*-azotoluene, m.p. 50°.

Different experiments have been done by using different quantities of sodium, keeping the amounts of *o*-nitrotoluene and methyl alcohol the same. It has been found that the maximum yield of *o*-azotoluene is obtained when 5 gms. of sodium are used and that by increasing the quantity of metallic sodium the yield of the azo-compound decreases with the corresponding increase of that of toluidine. The reaction mixture is heated for four or eight hours. The duration of heating has no appreciable change in the yield of the azotoluene. Along with *o*-azotoluene in all these experiments small quantities of *o*-azoxytoluene, *o*-toluidine, some resinous products and a small quantity of unaltered *o*-nitrotoluene have been obtained.

8. *Reduction by means of sodium ethylate.* In a few experiments sodium ethylate has been used in place of sodium methylate under similar conditions but with no better result. Here also small quantities of *o*-azoxytoluene, *o*-toluidine and some resinous products are obtained.

9. *Reduction by means of aluminium wire (or dust) and sodium hydroxide at 100°.* A series of experiments have been carried out using aluminium dust as a reducing agent in alkaline solutions. *o*-Nitrotoluene (6 g.) and methyl alcohol (150 c.c.) are put in a flask provided with a reflux condenser. A definite quantity of aluminium is then added and then a definite quantity of sodium hydroxide solution is dropped (5 c.c. at a time) from the top of the condenser at an interval of two minutes. The reaction is vigorous and the flask has therefore to be cooled from time to time to prevent the reaction from becoming too violent. When the whole of the sodium hydroxide solution has been added and the reaction slackened, the reaction product is heated on a water-bath for 8 hours. The product is then distilled to remove the alcohol and the solution

neutralised by means of dilute hydrochloric acid. The insoluble residue is removed by filtration and extracted by means of absolute alcohol. The alcoholic extract gave crystals which were recrystallised from the same solvent. *o*-Azotoluene and *o*-hydrazotoluene are separated by means of fractional crystallisation from alcohol. A very small quantity of *o*-toluidine has also been found in the product. A number of such experiments have been done using different amounts of aluminium dust and sodium hydroxide from which it is clear that a mixture of *o*-azotoluene and *o*-hydrazotoluene is always obtained. By increasing the quantity of aluminium dust or of sodium hydroxide solution there has been an almost proportionate increase in the yield of the products.

It is interesting to find that by using aluminium in the form of wire *o*-azotoluene only is obtained.

10. *Reduction by means of zinc dust in an alkaline medium.* The experimental details here are the same as in the case of aluminium dust. A very good yield of *o*-azotoluene (about 87 per cent.) is obtained by using 10 gm. of zinc dust and 30 gm. of caustic soda in 100 c.c. solution with 6 gms. of *o*-nitrotoluene. By increasing either the amount of zinc dust or of caustic soda, no appreciable change in the yield is observed.

11. *Reduction by means of stannous chloride in an alkaline solution.* The experimental details are mentioned under the formation of azoxytoluene. By using this reagent a certain quantity of *o*-azotoluene (about 62 per cent. of the total yield) is always obtained along with *o*-azoxytoluene. It has not been possible to get this product exclusively by increasing the quantity of the reducing agent.

12. *Reduction of *o*-azoxytoluene to *o*-azotoluene by means of iron dust.* By gently heating *o*-azoxytoluene directly over flame with iron dust in a tube, it has been possible to get some azotoluene condensed on the cooler parts of the tube but the yield is poor and other products, such as *o*-toluidine, have also been obtained in small quantities.

13. *Reduction of *o*-azoxytoluene to *o*-azotoluene by means of phosphorus pentachloride.* A better yield of *o*-azotoluene from *o*-azoxytoluene is, however, obtained by reduction with phosphorus pentachloride. *o*-Azoxytoluene (5 g.) is heated on a water-bath at 60°. Phosphorus pentachloride (about 3 g.) is then added. A vigorous reaction follows. When it has subsided, the products are washed with water to remove the excess of phosphorus pentachloride and

phosphorus oxychloride formed in the reaction. The solid residue is then dried and crystallised from absolute alcohol and thus pure azotoluene (2.5 g.) is obtained.

TABLE IIa₂
o-Nitrotoluene taken = 6 gm.

Expt.	Metallic sodium (gms.)	Methyl or ethyl alcohol	Time allowed for the reaction.	Percentage yield of azo-toluene,
		<i>Methyl alcohol.</i>		
1	4	100 c.c.	4 hrs.	39.2
2	5	"	"	47.9
3	4	"	8	39.2
4	5	"	"	47.9
5	8	"	"	39.2
6	10	"	"	33.1
		<i>Ethyl alcohol</i>		
7	5	100 c. c.	4	47.9
8	8	"	"	34.8

TABLE IIb₂
o-Nitrotoluene taken = 6 gm. Ethyl alcohol = 150 c.c.

Expt.	Reducing agent (gm.)	Sodium hydroxide.	Percentage yield of azo-compd.	Remarks.
	<i>Aluminium dust</i>			
1	7.5	30 g. in 100 c.c.	8.2	Main product— hydrazotoluene in expts. 1—3.
2	12.5	80 " "	10.9	
3	7.5	50 " "	10.9	
	<i>Aluminium wire</i>			
4	7.5	30 " "	43.5	
	<i>Zinc dust</i>			
5	10	30 " "	37.0	
6	15	30 " "	37.0	
7	7.5	30 " "	32.4	
8	7.5	40 " "	78.3	
9	10.0	3 " "	65.2 (azo) 13.1 (hydrazo)	Heated for 8 hrs.
	<i>Stannous chloride</i>			
10	7.5	15 " "	40.4 (azo) 21.1 (hydrazo)	

Reduction of o-Nitrotoluene to o-Hydrazotoluene.

14. *By means of aluminium dust in an alkaline solution.* The experimental details are given under reduction of *o*-nitrotoluene to *o*-azotoluene. A mixture of azo- and hydrazo-toluenes is always obtained by this method. Attempts to get exclusively only one product have failed. The maximum yield, about 47 per cent. is obtained by using 12.5 g. of aluminium dust and 30 g. of caustic soda for 6 g. of *o*-nitrotoluene.

15. *By means of zinc dust in an alkaline solution.* The experimental details are given under the reduction of *o*-nitrotoluene to *o*-azotoluene. The yield is still poor, being only about 13 per cent.

16a. *Reduction of o-azotoluene to o-hydrazotoluene.* A better yield of *o*-hydrazotoluene (about 75%), is obtained by reducing *o*-azotoluene by means of alcoholic ammonium sulphide. *o*-Azotoluene is dissolved in alcohol and excess of ammonium sulphide added and the reacting mixture allowed to stand for six hours. A solid separates out. If the mixture is kept at a higher temperature, the reaction seems to proceed more quickly.

16b. A still better yield of *o*-hydrazotoluene (about 95%) is obtained if ammonia is added to a solution of *o*-azotoluene in alcohol and a steady current of hydrogen sulphide is passed for about one hour.

TABLE III.

Expt.	Substance to be reduced (in gm.).	Reducing agent (in gm.).	Sodium hydroxide (in gm. in 100 c.c.).	Methyl-alcohol (in c.c.).	Time allowed for the reaction.	Percentage yield of hydrazo-toluene.
<i>o</i> -Nitrotoluene Aluminium						
1	6	7.5	30	150	6 hrs. on W.B.	34.5
2	"	12.5	"	"	" "	45.2
3	"	7.5	50	"	" "	38.8
4	"	10	30	"	8 "	12.9
<i>Azotoluene</i>						
5	4	<i>Ammonium sulphide</i>	—	100	6 hrs. at room temp.	74.2
6	4	H ₂ S	—	"	1 " "	94

Reduction of o-Nitrotoluene to o-Toluidine.

Small quantities of *o*-toluidine are obtained in the products when sodium methoxide, sodium ethoxide and aluminium dust are used as reducing agents. A better yield of *o*-toluidine (about 70%) is obtained when *o*-nitrotoluene is reduced by means of sodium disulphide. This reagent is prepared by adding sulphur to a boiling aqueous solution of sodium sulphide till it dissolves no more of sulphur. *o*-Nitrotoluene (10 g.) is taken in a flask provided with an upright condenser, alcohol (100 c. c.) and sodium disulphide solution are added and the mixture is heated on a water-bath for 3 to 4 hours. The alcohol is then distilled off. A layer of *o*-nitrotoluene and *o*-toluidine separates out. They are separated by steam distillation.

A still better yield (about 83%) is obtained by reducing *o*-nitrotoluene by means of tin and hydrochloric acid. Here the process is the same as in the case of nitrobenzene.

o-Toluidine has also been obtained in fairly a good yield (80%) by reducing *o*-azotoluene by means of stannous chloride in an acid medium. Here *o*-azotoluene (6 g.) is taken in a flask provided with a reflux condenser and stannous chloride (10 g.) in hydrochloric acid (35-40 c. c.) is added. Alcohol (100 c. c.) is then added to it and the reaction mixture heated on a water-bath for 3 to 4 hours. After removal of alcohol, the residue is treated with water, and *o*-toluidine separated.

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